

A Study of Charge Point Infrastructure Policies on EV Driver Satisfaction

Peter Fussey, Akintomiwa Akin-Onigbinde, and Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos University of Sussex

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Abstract

This paper presents a simulation approach to assess the impact of changes to the charge point infrastructure and policies on Electric Vehicle (EV) user satisfaction, combining both market drivers with the practicalities of EV usage. An agent-based model (ABM) approach is developed where a large number of EVs, that represent the user population, drive within a region of interest. By simulating the driver's response to their charging experience, the model allows large scale trends to emerge from the population to guide infrastructure policies as the number of EVs increases beyond the initial early adopter market.

The model incorporates a Monte Carlo approach to generate EV and driver agent instances with distinct characteristics, including battery size, vehicle type, driving style, sensitivity to range. The driver model is constructed

to respond to events that may increase range anxiety, e.g. increasing the likelihood of charging as the driver becomes more anxious.

A charge point infrastructure and EV population scenario is simulated, including a queuing system for charge stations. The impact on EV driver satisfaction of new policies, including the number of charge points, power rating of charge points, pricing models, green energy providers and numbers of EVs is simulated. The driver satisfaction is assessed by combining a number of metrics, e.g. range anxiety metric, time spent in queues through to access to the desired brand or green energy.

As the number of EVs increase, the policies need to focus on the efficient use of existing charge points to maintain customer satisfaction. The study uses the results to consider the balance between the minimum requirements and value enhancing requirements for customer satisfaction.

Introduction

Sales of EVs are increasing rapidly with a 35% year on year increase in 2022 and the share of EVs in total car sales rising from 9% in 2021 to 14% in 2022, [1]. The transition from combustion engine vehicles to EVs requires a significant change in behaviour that may lead to unforeseen consequences that may slow the adoption of EVs.

EV user experience has been reviewed in [2] and covers topics such as range anxiety, changes to route planning, changes to driving style through to the introduction of regenerative braking. The use of policies to affect EV charge station efficiency is studied in [3] which showed that financial incentives for encouraging EV users to move their EV once it is charged may be effective in improving the efficiency of EV charging stations.

As the number of EVs increases, the charging experience is becoming more complex with new and interdependent behaviours emerging. There are few studies of these

emerging charging experiences, potentially because early adopters have access to home charging or charge stations on routes have been largely underutilized.

In this paper we introduce an agent-based model (ABM) to study the EV driver satisfaction during charging when different infrastructure policies are considered and use it to extrapolate to study increasing numbers of EVs. Key contributions from this work are:

- A flexible tool to assess the impact of infrastructure policies at a charge station level on EV driver satisfaction,
- A study of emerging behaviours from the EV population, for example, queues at charge stations when all the charge points are occupied leading to an increase in range anxiety.

A brief note on terminology, to describe the charging infrastructure, the following terms are used in this paper;

a charge point is a place where one vehicle can be charged whilst a charge station is a group of charge points. For example, a charge station can be found at a service station, carpark or a shopping centre.

Modelling Approach

Introduction to Agent Based Modelling

Agent-based modelling is an approach that simulates interactions between various 'agents', as well as their individual and collective behaviour within a specific environment. For example, in a traffic simulation, an agent may be a vehicle, with the environment defined by the roads. It is an established means to simulate and study the interactions of complex systems and has been applied to many situations, for example evacuation modelling, customer flow in supermarkets through to traffic simulations [4] and EV charging [5].

An ABM is built from the bottom up, modelling the system at a microscopic level of detail to then allow the macroscopic behaviour to emerge. It is suitable for systems that have nonlinear individual behaviour (e.g. rule based logic or thresholds), behaviour that exhibits memory and adaption, as well as interactions that are heterogeneous (e.g. depend on the individual agent), [6]

This makes ABM suitable for the detailed study of changes to the EV charging infrastructure and policies, such as how the number of charge points or pricing strategy may influence EV user satisfaction. By modelling individual EVs, the ABM can also study the impact of increasing numbers of EVs on EV behaviour and satisfaction.

Considering agents in more detail, [7], an agent is identifiable, self-contained and discrete with a set of characteristics and rules that govern its behaviour. The agent can interact with other agents in the environment and these agents can be the same type or different types of agents. Agents can learn over time to adapt their behaviours based on their experience within their environment.

Defining an EV Charging ABM

This model sets out to simulate the behaviour of EV drivers as they charge their EVs. The model is built up from three agent types, to allow the various interactions to be simulated; an EV agent, a Charge Station (CS) agent and a Location agent, [Figure 1](#). The model is initialized and the agents carry out their actions as time progresses, using a discrete timestep.

Model Structure

The model uses a staged random scheduler for agent activation. This means that agents are selected at random to run their 'step' functions, stage-by-stage, once, every timestep. Each agent's 'step' functions are discussed later in this section.

The model environment is a grid of cells. Each cell can contain any number of agents at any one time. During a

FIGURE 1 Overview of the agents in the ABM.

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run, the model agents exist at various locations on the grid using positional coordinates. The EV agents are mobile and move during the simulation, while other agents (Charge Stations and Location agents) are fixed in space.

EV Agent 'Step' Functions

EV definition: The EV agent models both the EV and driver. The initial parameters of the agent are generated using a Monte Carlo method from a distribution of typical EV characteristics. Each EV has its own characteristics such as battery size, average speed and electrical energy consumption that are generated. The agent has additional parameters associated with the driver, for example the maximum price for electricity, an initial 'range anxiety' and 'customer satisfaction', the destination location, journey start time for each day and probability of having home charging available.

EV move: The EV agent moves between locations, using energy as it moves, depleting the battery. The EV agent has a state machine, [Figure 2](#), that manages this behaviour, from 'idle' to 'travel' for example. As the battery state of charge (SOC) reduces below a threshold, the EV moves to state 'travel low' where it is looking for a suitable place to charge the battery. The EV can now look for a nearby charge station.

EV charge: On arriving at a charge station, the EV checks if there are available charge points. If there are no charge points, it joins the charge station queue, otherwise it starts to charge. The charge rate is calculated from the maximum of the EV charge acceptance and the charge point power rating. The EV is charged to 80% SOC and then leaves the charge station to complete its journey.

EV queue: The EV joins the queue at the charge station which follows a 'first in first out' procedure. This provides a link between EV agent and charge station agent.

FIGURE 2 Overview of the EV state machine.

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Exceptions: The model requires a number of exception procedures to ensure that EVs are able to continue with the simulation and do not get stuck or stranded. This involves a recovery action that takes the EV to the destination and charges the battery back to 100% SOC. Exceptions include; recovery if battery SOC is zero, recovery if the EV is in the queue at the charge station at the end of the day.

EV driver response: The EV driver response is modelled with two parameters; range anxiety (RA), and customer satisfaction (CSat).

RA is a parameter that varies from 0 to 1, with 0 being no anxiety and 1 being very anxious. RA is also a parameter that affects the behaviour of the EV driver by changing the battery SOC threshold at which the driver starts looking for a charge point (i.e. the transition to 'travel low'). A more anxious driver will have a higher SOC threshold and will therefore start to look for a charge station earlier than a less anxious driver. The RA is updated every day, decreasing by an amount if successfully arriving at the destination or increasing by a different amount if the EV is stranded.

CSat is a parameter that varies from 0 to 1, with 0 being dissatisfied and 1 being satisfied. CSat does not affect the behaviour of the model. The CSat parameter is updated every day, increasing if the queue time was below a threshold and decreasing if the queue time is above a threshold.

The use of two parameters is based on the customer satisfaction models that consider minimum service requirements and value enhancing service requirements [8]. In this model the RA is used to reflect minimum service requirements related to getting stranded. Whilst CSat reflects the value enhancing requirements by considering the time spent in queues.

Charge Station Agent

CS definition: The CS agent includes a model of the queue and the occupancy of the CS. The input information includes the location of the charge station, the number of charge points together with a set of information associated with each charge point (e.g. charge power, price of electricity and so on).

CS queue: The CS queue is managed on a first in, first out basis.

Location Agent

Location definition: The location agent is defined by its location, as a source or destination for the EVs. It is only used to track the EVs.

Case Studies

The following studies were undertaken. The influence of such factors should be understood by policymakers when evaluating the impact of EV-related policies, which is key to their successful implementation.

- Baseline model study, as a benchmark.
- Study of the influence of the number of EVs.
- Study of the influence of the number of charge points.
- Study of the influence of battery sizes.

Simulation Results with Baseline Model

The model has been tested using a simplified model of southern England, [Figure 3](#), to validate functionality and provide initial insight into how policy and infrastructure updates may affect EV user satisfaction.

The process for running the model is as follows:

1. Set up the model with the charge station locations and details,
2. Populate the model with a number of EV agents taken from a series of input parameter distributions,
3. Allow the EV models to drive around the network and observe how range anxiety and customer satisfaction evolve for different input parameters.

Inputs and Configuration of the Model

The configuration information for the model includes run-specific information, such as the number of EVs, number of timesteps and the time resolution for the run. Other model-level inputs include flags for enabling specific features in the model. Some of these options such as overnight charge directly impact the dynamics of the model while others such as logging, and data export do not. Other model characteristics, such as the specific size of the model's space and its visualization dimensions are also necessary inputs.

Other configuration information includes specific input probability distributions for specific agent attributes. For EVs this includes battery size, price threshold, journey start time, and model constants for the EVs energy

FIGURE 3 Baseline simulation region, circles represent charge station locations and crosses represent the location agents.

TABLE 1 Input data to model for Monte Carlo method.

Data	Values and sources
Battery Size [kWh]	Normal distribution with mean of 55 kWh and standard deviation of 5 kWh
Vehicle average speed [km/h]	Taken from a uniform distribution between 40 and 80 kph
Electricity consumption [kW/km]	A function of vehicle speed: $consumption = 0.5 + 0.05 \times speed$
Price threshold	Normal distribution (mean and standard deviation)
Journey start time	Two normal distributions to cover morning and afternoon journeys.

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consumption. The Charge Station agents are parameterized using information including the agent's location and charge point characteristics (power ratings and price of electricity).

The model has been set up with the following data provided in [Table 1](#).

Initialisation of the Model and Discussion of Results

Range anxiety: The model is initialised with a range anxiety parameter, $RA = 0.5$, and customer satisfaction, $CSat = 0.5$. These are parameters that the model is being used to calculate. As the population of EVs drive around the network, the RA is updated. An example evolution in [Figure 4](#) shows the distribution of RA over time for 500 EVs where the colour represents the density of vehicles. Low density is blue and high density is yellow. The simulation starts with all the vehicles at 0.5 and as the vehicles complete successful journeys, the RA falls by a small amount, referred to as 'decRA'.

As the RA falls, some of the vehicles start to have a low SOC at the start of the day and risk not being able to get to a charge station to charge and complete their journey. In this case, their RA increases by an amount, referred to as 'incRA'. Since there is a range of different

characteristics for the vehicles, this results in a distribution of responses. After each increase in RA, the value of 'incRA' is reduced to allow the RA to converge on a stable value by effectively carrying out a bounded search of the RA space, which can be loosely interpreted as the EV user becoming acclimatized to the situation and building a habitual behaviour. [Figure 4](#) presents the RA distribution across the simulated fleet, the average RA over time and the final RA distribution at the end of the simulation.

Individual vehicle responses: To help understand the model further, a number of vehicle parameters for the first three vehicles are presented in [Figure 5](#). The plots

FIGURE 4 Evolution of range anxiety, the left plot shows the distribution of EVs over a 300 day simulation, from initial value of 0.5. The right plot shows the final distribution (average over last 20 days) and the lower plot shows the moving average of RA across the fleet of vehicles.

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FIGURE 5 Detailed results for three EVs. The graphs are intended to illustrate the overall behaviour rather than specific results. For example, the range of SOC during the simulation, the evolution of RA and Customer Satisfaction, the states being dominated by 'idle' and 'travel' with intermittent charging and the range of routes that cover all the locations.

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show; the battery state of charge (SOC), the RA parameter, the CSat parameter, the operating mode and the route (e.g. A-B indicates the EV is going from A to B).

The SOC plot shows the range of battery that is utilized by the EVs starts at around 50% to 80%. This is because the RA is set to 50% which means the EVs start to look for a charge station once the battery SOC gets to 50%. As the RA falls, a greater battery range is used, but this increases the risk of getting stranded. The RA then rises to a point where the utilized range is maximized whilst the probability of the EVs getting stranded is minimized.

The RA plot shows the different evolutions of the RA for each vehicle. This is because each vehicle has a different 'decRA' value, to replicate drivers having a different appetite for risk.

The customer satisfaction plot shows it is held constant for the first 200 days and then allowed to evolve. This is so that the CSat parameter reflects the EV driver satisfaction once the RA has stabilized. If this parameter is enabled at the start, it will be affected by the events during the initial calibration phase. The evolution of the CSat parameter reflects the time that the EVs spend in queues, reducing when the queue is too long and improving when the queue is short.

The operating mode plot shows the EV agents spending most of their time between 'idle' and 'travel' with occasional 'low batt' and subsequent 'charge' events. At this scale we can also see the 'stranded' events during the calibration phase, that are then reduced once the model is calibrated. Figure 6 provides a zoom into the operating mode plot to provide more details of the queuing behaviour where the queues occur prior to charge events.

The route plot provides a snapshot of which locations the EVs have visited and shows they have a good coverage of the various routes in the model.

Figure 7 presents the summary results for both the RA and CSat parameters. Here it can be seen that the customer satisfaction is low because of the length of time spent in queues. Note, only the RA changes the behaviour of the EV agent, the CSat does not affect the actions of the EV agent but provides subjective feedback.

FIGURE 6 Zoom into operating modes to show queuing prior to charge event.

FIGURE 7 Averaged results of range anxiety and customer satisfaction for a fleet of 500 EVs.

Policy and Infrastructure Study

Study of Number of EVs

The first study with the model is to consider the number of EVs, to provide insight into how the performance of the infrastructure may evolve as more EVs are on the roads. Since the model is scalable, this only requires changing the number of EVs parameter and a larger fleet is created using the Monte Carlo approach.

The model has been run with the following numbers of EVs; 20, 100, 200, 300, 500, 750 and 1000. For each run, the final range anxiety and customer satisfaction have been recorded and presented in Figure 8.

The response from the model shows that the number of EVs has little impact on range anxiety, however it does have a strong impact on customer satisfaction.

This is because when there are lots of EVs, the main impact is increasing the length of queues at charge stations. In this case, increasing the range anxiety – which increases the number of times the vehicles visit the charge stations – does not help manage or reduce the queue length.

FIGURE 8 Averaged results of range anxiety and customer satisfaction as a function of the number of EVs.

Conversely, the customer satisfaction becomes very low as the number of EVs start to saturate the charging network and the EV wait time increases.

Study of Number of Charge Points

The first policy change is to study the impact of increasing the number of charge points. This can be done uniformly, or a targeted approach can be taken. Figure 9 presents the sum of the number of EVs in queues during the simulation with 500 EVs.

From this 'heat map' of charge point queues, 3 additional charge points were placed at each of the top 3 charge stations. This successfully reduced the queues at these locations, as shown in Figure 10.

The customer satisfaction is defined by time spent in queues, decreasing if too long and increasing if the time is below a threshold. This is demonstrated by the significant impact on the customer satisfaction, which rose from 11% to 37% in response to adding the new charge points, whilst the range anxiety was similar in both cases.

Study of Pricing Policy on user Behaviour

The second policy studied with this model is the impact of charge point prices on user behaviour. In the model, each EV agent has their own preferred pricing and will search for charge points that are below or equal to their desired price.

The charge points are configured with pricing information that is related to the charging power available, with fast chargers more expensive than slower chargers, Figure 11. The EV agents are given a preferred price from a distribution. The prices are presented as a normalized price per kWh, from 0 to 1.

FIGURE 9 A 'heat map' showing where the most queues have formed. Size of circle indicates number of vehicles queuing over the simulation at each charge station.

FIGURE 10 Reduction in queues at the targeted charge stations.

FIGURE 11 Pricing structure, with a normalized price per kWh.

In this study, the mean of the EV agent preferred price distribution was reduced from 0.7 to 0.5. The model was run with 200 EVs and the customer satisfaction was found to reduce from 39% to 19% as the mean was reduced. This was because the EVs were then forced to look for the cheaper electricity and more queues formed around these charge points, the impact of which was magnified as these charge points were also slower.

The model has been used to study the impact of pricing strategies on customer satisfaction as well as revenue generation.

Study of Battery Sizes

The initial simulation was run with a distribution of battery sizes with a mean of 55 kWh and a standard deviation of 5 kWh. The model was re-run with two groups of battery size, one with mean 40 kWh and the second with extended capacity of 70 kWh. For each battery set-up, the models were run with 500EVs. Figure 12 shows the vehicles with a smaller battery tend to have a higher range anxiety

FIGURE 12 Range anxiety versus battery size.

which is as expected. This offers an initial validation of the chosen implementation of range anxiety.

Summary and Conclusions

This paper has presented a new tool to assess and explore charge point infrastructure policy decisions on EV driver behaviour and subsequent satisfaction. An Agent Based Model is used to allow investigations to be carried out into the specific details of charge point infrastructure. By allowing the size of the EV population to be defined as a variable, the model can consider how the current and new infrastructure will cope as the number of EVs increase. At this simulation stage, the model has already been used to provide insight into increasing EV population and updating the number of charge points. The model has also been extended to analyse the impact of these policies on EVs with different battery sizes. The studies undertaken mainly serve as preliminary validation of the model, but the following key conclusions were also drawn:

- As EV uptake increases, the queues in charging stations increase, which has an adverse effect on satisfaction.
- Additional charging stations were shown to significantly reduce queues, as expected.
- Varying the price has an impact on the user behaviour and subsequently affects the overall population's customer satisfaction.
- The size of the EV's battery was shown to be inversely proportional to the driver's range anxiety, as expected.

The queue has been implemented as a first in first out queue, however this may not reflect reality at charging stations. Indeed, queuing behaviour is likely to become a

challenge as the increase in numbers of EVs outpaces the increase in number of charge points. For new charge stations, there is the opportunity to build in queue infrastructure to direct EVs into queues, however this will not apply to all charge stations so alternative approaches will be required. For example, implementing a virtual queue where EVs can take a 'ticket' on arrival or a booking system to reserve the charging space and time. However, these will also require integration with the charge point services and it is likely they will need some form of incentive to ensure EVs are not occupying reserved charge points.

The model is currently being calibrated to real world data from the demonstration sites within the EU project eCharge4Drivers and this validation will be presented in a subsequent paper.

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Contact Information

Peter Fussey,
University of Sussex, Falmer, BN1 9QT, UK.
p.m.fussey@sussex.ac.uk

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Definitions/Abbreviations

ABM - Agent Based Model

CS - Charge Station

CSat - Customer Satisfaction

EV - Electric Vehicle

RA - Range anxiety

SOC - Battery State of Charge